

DOUBT \mathcal{N} -IDEAL THEORY IN BCK -ALGEBRAS BASED ON \mathcal{N} -STRUCTURES

ANAS AL-MASARWAH *, ABD GHAFUR AHMAD AND G. MUHIUDDIN

ABSTRACT. The notions of doubt \mathcal{N} -subalgebras and doubt \mathcal{N} -ideals in BCK -algebras are introduced, and related properties are investigated. Characterizations of a doubt \mathcal{N} -subalgebra and a doubt \mathcal{N} -ideal are given, and relations between them are discussed.

1. INTRODUCTION

The study of BCK -algebras was introduced by Imai and Iséki [10] in 1966. BCK -algebras have been applied to many branches of mathematics, such as functional analysis, group theory, topology, probability theory.

A crisp set C in a universe \mathcal{X} is a function $\lambda_C : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ yielding the value 0 for elements excluded from the set C and the value 1 for elements belonging to the set C . As a generalization of crisp sets, Zadeh [17] introduced the degree of positive membership in 1965 and defined the fuzzy sets. Jun et al. [12] presented a new function which is called negative-valued function, and developed \mathcal{N} -structures as a one of the hybrid models of fuzzy sets. They applied \mathcal{N} -structures in BCK -algebras and proposed \mathcal{N} -subalgebras and \mathcal{N} -ideals [12]. In [11], Jun established the definition of doubt fuzzy subalgebras and ideals in BCK -algebras. After that, many Hybrid models of fuzzy sets were applied in BCK -algebras and other algebraic structures [5, 6, 8, 7, 9, 4, 15, 16, 2, 1, 3, 14, 13].

In this paper, we discuss an \mathcal{N} -structure with an application to BCK -algebras. We introduce the notions of doubt \mathcal{N} -subalgebras and doubt \mathcal{N} -ideals in BCK -algebras, and investigate related properties. Then, we present some characterizations of them by means of doubt level subset. Moreover, relations between a doubt \mathcal{N} -subalgebra and a doubt \mathcal{N} -ideal in BCK -algebras are discussed.

2. PRELIMINARIES

In this section, we include some basic definitions and preliminary facts about BCK -algebras which are essential for our results.

By a BCK -algebra, we mean an algebra $(\mathcal{X}; *, 0)$ of type $(2, 0)$ satisfying the following axioms for all $x, y, z \in \mathcal{X}$:

$$(I) ((x * y) * (x * z)) * (z * y) = 0,$$

2010 *Mathematics Subject Classification.* 06F35, 03G25, 03B52, 03B05.

Key words and phrases. BCK/BCI -algebra; \mathcal{N} -structures; Doubt \mathcal{N} -subalgebra; Doubt \mathcal{N} -ideal.

Received: February 29, 2020. Accepted: April 25, 2020.

*Corresponding author.

- (II) $(x * (x * y)) * y = 0$,
- (III) $x * x = 0$,
- (IV) $0 * x = 0$,
- (V) $x * y = 0$ and $y * x = 0$ imply $x = y$.

Any BCK -algebra \mathcal{X} satisfies the following axioms for all $x, y, z \in \mathcal{X}$:

- (11) $x * 0 = x$,
- (12) $(x * y) * z = (x * z) * y$,
- (13) $x * y \leq x$,
- (14) $(x * y) * z \leq (x * z) * (y * z)$,
- (15) $x \leq y \Rightarrow x * z \leq y * z, z * y \leq z * x$.

A partial ordering \leq on a BCK -algebra \mathcal{X} can be defined by $x \leq y$ if and only if $x * y = 0$. A non-empty subset K of a BCK -algebra \mathcal{X} is called a subalgebra of \mathcal{X} if $x * y \in K, \forall x, y \in \mathcal{X}$, and an ideal of \mathcal{X} if $\forall x, y \in \mathcal{X}$,

- (1) $0 \in K$,
- (2) $x * y \in K$ and $y \in K$ imply $x \in K$.

Definition 2.1. [11] A fuzzy set $A = \{(x, \mu_A(x)) \mid x \in \mathcal{X}\}$ in \mathcal{X} is called a doubt fuzzy subalgebra of \mathcal{X} if $\mu_A(x * y) \leq \max\{\mu_A(x), \mu_A(y)\}$ for all $x, y \in \mathcal{X}$.

Definition 2.2. [11] A fuzzy set $A = \{(x, \mu_A(x)) \mid x \in \mathcal{X}\}$ in \mathcal{X} is called a doubt fuzzy ideal of \mathcal{X} if $\mu_A(0) \leq \mu_A(x)$ and $\mu_A(x) \leq \max\{\mu_A(x * y), \mu_A(y)\}$ for all $x, y \in \mathcal{X}$.

Denote by $\mathcal{F}(\mathcal{X}, [-1, 0])$ the collection of functions from a set \mathcal{X} to the interval $[-1, 0]$. We say that, an element of $\mathcal{F}(\mathcal{X}, [-1, 0])$ is a negative-valued function from \mathcal{X} to $[-1, 0]$ (briefly, \mathcal{N} -function on \mathcal{X}). By an \mathcal{N} -structure we mean an ordered pair (\mathcal{X}, ϕ) , where ϕ is an \mathcal{N} -function on \mathcal{X} . In what follows, let \mathcal{X} be a BCK -algebra and ϕ an \mathcal{N} -function on \mathcal{X} unless otherwise specified.

In [12], Jun et al. introduced the concepts of \mathcal{N} -subalgebras and \mathcal{N} -ideals in BCK -algebras as follows:

Definition 2.3. An \mathcal{N} -structure (\mathcal{X}, ϕ) is called an \mathcal{N} -subalgebra of \mathcal{X} if for all $x, y \in \mathcal{X}$:

$$\phi(x * y) \leq \max\{\phi(x), \phi(y)\}.$$

Definition 2.4. An \mathcal{N} -structure (\mathcal{X}, ϕ) is called an \mathcal{N} -ideal of \mathcal{X} if for all $x, y \in \mathcal{X}$:

- (1) $\phi(0) \leq \phi(x)$,
- (2) $\phi(x) \leq \max\{\phi(x * y), \phi(y)\}$.

3. DOUBT \mathcal{N} -SUBALGEBRAS AND \mathcal{N} -IDEALS

In this section, we introduce doubt \mathcal{N} -subalgebras and ideals in BCK -algebras and investigate some of their properties.

Definition 3.1. An \mathcal{N} -structure (\mathcal{X}, ϕ) is called a doubt \mathcal{N} -subalgebra of \mathcal{X} if for all $x, y \in \mathcal{X}$:

$$\phi(x * y) \geq \min\{\phi(x), \phi(y)\}.$$

Example 3.2. Consider a *BCK*-algebra $X = \{0, a, b, c\}$ with the following Cayley table:

*	0	a	b	c
0	0	0	0	0
a	a	0	0	a
b	b	a	0	b
c	c	c	c	0

Let (\mathcal{X}, φ) be an \mathcal{N} -structure in which φ is given by

$$\varphi(x) = \begin{cases} -0.2, & \text{if } x=0 \\ -0.3, & \text{if } x=a, b \\ -0.8, & \text{if } x=c. \end{cases}$$

By routine calculation, we know that (\mathcal{X}, φ) is a doubt \mathcal{N} -subalgebra of \mathcal{X} .

For any \mathcal{N} -function φ and $\alpha \in [-1, 0]$, we define the set

$$\varphi_\alpha = \{x \in \mathcal{X} : \varphi(x) \geq \alpha\}.$$

Theorem 3.1. Let (\mathcal{X}, φ) be an \mathcal{N} -structure over \mathcal{X} and let $\alpha \in [-1, 0]$. If (\mathcal{X}, φ) is a doubt \mathcal{N} -subalgebra of \mathcal{X} , then the nonempty set φ_α is a subalgebra of \mathcal{X} .

Proof. Let $\alpha \in [-1, 0]$ and let $\varphi_\alpha \neq \emptyset$. If $x, y \in \varphi_\alpha$, then $\varphi(x) \geq \alpha$ and $\varphi(y) \geq \alpha$. It follows from Definition 3.1 that

$$\varphi(x * y) \geq \min\{\varphi(x), \varphi(y)\} \geq \alpha.$$

Hence, $x * y \in \varphi_\alpha$, and therefore φ_α is a subalgebra of \mathcal{X} . \square

Theorem 3.2. Let (\mathcal{X}, φ) be an \mathcal{N} -structure over \mathcal{X} and assume that $\emptyset \neq \varphi_\alpha$ is a subalgebra of \mathcal{X} for all $\alpha \in [-1, 0]$. Then, (\mathcal{X}, φ) is a doubt \mathcal{N} -subalgebra of \mathcal{X} .

Proof. Assume that $\emptyset \neq \varphi_\alpha$ is a subalgebra of \mathcal{X} for all $\alpha \in [-1, 0]$. If there exist $a', b' \in \mathcal{X}$ such that

$$\varphi(a' * b') < \min\{\varphi(a'), \varphi(b')\}.$$

Then by taking

$$\alpha_o = \frac{1}{2}[\varphi(a' * b') + \min\{\varphi(a'), \varphi(b')\}],$$

we have

$$\varphi(a' * b') < \alpha_o < \min\{\varphi(a'), \varphi(b')\}.$$

Hence, $a' * b' \notin \varphi_{\alpha_o}$, $a' \in \varphi_{\alpha_o}$ and $b' \in \varphi_{\alpha_o}$. This is a contradiction. Therefore, (\mathcal{X}, φ) is a doubt \mathcal{N} -subalgebra of \mathcal{X} . \square

Theorem 3.3. If (\mathcal{X}, φ) is a doubt \mathcal{N} -subalgebra of \mathcal{X} , then $\varphi(0) \geq \varphi(x)$ for all $x \in \mathcal{X}$.

Proof. For any $x \in \mathcal{X}$, we have $\varphi(0) = \varphi(x * x) \geq \min\{\varphi(x), \varphi(x)\} = \varphi(x)$. This completes the proof. \square

Theorem 3.4. If every doubt \mathcal{N} -subalgebra (\mathcal{X}, φ) of \mathcal{X} , satisfies

$$\varphi(x * y) \geq \varphi(y)$$

for all $x, y \in \mathcal{X}$, then (\mathcal{X}, φ) is constant.

Proof. Note that in a *BCK*-algebra \mathcal{X} , $x * 0 = x$ for all $x \in \mathcal{X}$. Since $\varphi(x * y) \geq \varphi(y)$, we have

$$\varphi(x) = \varphi(x * 0) \geq \varphi(0).$$

It follows from Theorem 3.3 that $\varphi(x) = \varphi(0)$ for all $x, y \in \mathcal{X}$. Therefore, (\mathcal{X}, φ) is constant. \square

Now, we introduce the notion of doubt \mathcal{N} -ideals in BCK -algebras.

Definition 3.3. An \mathcal{N} -structure (\mathcal{X}, φ) is called a doubt \mathcal{N} -ideal of \mathcal{X} if for all $x, y \in \mathcal{X}$:

- (1) $\varphi(0) \geq \varphi(x)$,
- (2) $\varphi(x) \geq \min\{\varphi(x * y), \varphi(y)\}$.

Example 3.4. Consider a BCK -algebra $X = \{0, a, b, c\}$ which is given in Example 3.6. Let (\mathcal{X}, φ) be an \mathcal{N} -structure in which φ is defined by

$$\varphi(x) = \begin{cases} -0.2, & \text{if } x=0 \\ -0.3, & \text{if } x=a, b \\ -0.8, & \text{if } x=c. \end{cases}$$

By routine calculation, we know that (\mathcal{X}, φ) is a doubt \mathcal{N} -ideal of \mathcal{X} .

Theorem 3.5. Let (\mathcal{X}, φ) be a doubt \mathcal{N} -ideal of \mathcal{X} . If \leq is a partial ordering on \mathcal{X} , then $\varphi(x) \geq \varphi(y)$ for all $x, y \in \mathcal{X}$ such that $x \leq y$.

Proof. Let (\mathcal{X}, φ) be a doubt \mathcal{N} -ideal of \mathcal{X} . It is known that \leq is a partial ordering on \mathcal{X} defined by $x \leq y$ if and only if $x * y = 0$ for all $x, y \in \mathcal{X}$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi(x) &\geq \min\{\varphi(x * y), \varphi(y)\} \\ &= \min\{\varphi(0), \varphi(y)\} \\ &= \varphi(y). \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. \square

Theorem 3.6. Let (\mathcal{X}, φ) be a doubt \mathcal{N} -ideal of \mathcal{X} . Then,

$$\varphi(x * y) \geq \varphi((x * y) * y) \Leftrightarrow \varphi((x * z) * (y * z)) \geq \varphi((x * y) * z)$$

for all $x, y, z \in \mathcal{X}$.

Proof. Note that

$$\begin{aligned} ((x * (y * z)) * z) * z &= ((x * z) * (y * z)) * z \\ &\leq (x * y) * z \end{aligned}$$

for all $x, y, z \in \mathcal{X}$. Assume that $\varphi(x * y) \geq \varphi((x * y) * y)$ for all $x, y, z \in \mathcal{X}$. It follows from (I2) and Theorem 3.5 that

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi((x * z) * (y * z)) &= \varphi((x * (y * z)) * z) \\ &\geq \varphi(((x * (y * z)) * z) * z) \\ &\geq \varphi((x * y) * z), \end{aligned}$$

for all $x, y, z \in \mathcal{X}$.

Conversely, suppose that

$$\varphi((x * z) * (y * z)) \geq \varphi((x * y) * z) \tag{3.1}$$

for all $x, y, z \in \mathcal{X}$. If we substitute z for y in Equation (3.1), then

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi(x * z) &= \varphi((x * z) * 0) \\ &= \varphi((x * z) * (z * z)) \\ &\geq \varphi((x * z) * z), \end{aligned}$$

for all $x, z \in \mathcal{X}$ by using (III) and (II.) □

Theorem 3.7. *Let (\mathcal{X}, φ) be a doubt \mathcal{N} -ideal of \mathcal{X} . Then,*

$$\varphi(x * y) \geq \min\{\varphi(x * z), \varphi(z * y)\}$$

for all $x, y, z \in \mathcal{X}$.

Proof. Note that $((x * y) * (x * z)) \leq (z * y)$ for all $x, y, z \in \mathcal{X}$. It follows from Theorem 3.5, that

$$\varphi((x * y) * (x * z)) \geq \varphi(z * y).$$

Now, by Definition 3.3, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi(x * y) &\geq \min\{\varphi((x * y) * (x * z)), \varphi(x * z)\} \\ &\geq \min\{\varphi(x * z), \varphi(z * y)\} \end{aligned}$$

for all $x, y, z \in \mathcal{X}$. This completes the proof. □

Theorem 3.8. *Let (\mathcal{X}, φ) be a doubt \mathcal{N} -ideal of \mathcal{X} . Then,*

$$\varphi(x * (x * y)) \geq \varphi(y)$$

for all $x, y \in \mathcal{X}$.

Proof. Let (\mathcal{X}, φ) be a doubt \mathcal{N} -ideal of \mathcal{X} . Then, for all $x, y \in \mathcal{X}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi(x * (x * y)) &\geq \min\{\varphi((x * (x * y)) * y), \varphi(y)\} \\ &= \min\{\varphi((x * y) * (x * y)), \varphi(y)\} \\ &= \min\{\varphi(0), \varphi(y)\} \\ &= \varphi(y). \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. □

Theorem 3.9. *Let (\mathcal{X}, φ) be an \mathcal{N} -structure over \mathcal{X} and let $\alpha \in [-1, 0]$. If (\mathcal{X}, φ) is a doubt \mathcal{N} -ideal of \mathcal{X} , then the nonempty set φ_α is an ideal of \mathcal{X} .*

Proof. Assume that $\varphi_\alpha \neq \emptyset$ for $\alpha \in [-1, 0]$. Clearly, $0 \in \varphi_\alpha$. Let $x * y \in \varphi_\alpha$ and $y \in \varphi_\alpha$. Then, $\varphi(x * y) \geq \alpha$ and $\varphi(y) \geq \alpha$. It follows from Definition 3.3 that

$$\varphi(x) \geq \min\{\varphi(x * y), \varphi(y)\} \geq \alpha,$$

so, $x \in \varphi_\alpha$. Therefore, φ_α is an ideal of \mathcal{X} . □

Theorem 3.10. *Let (\mathcal{X}, φ) be an \mathcal{N} -structure over \mathcal{X} and assume that $\emptyset \neq \varphi_\alpha$ is an ideal of \mathcal{X} for all $\alpha \in [-1, 0]$. Then, (\mathcal{X}, φ) is a doubt \mathcal{N} -ideal of \mathcal{X} .*

Proof. Assume that $\emptyset \neq \varphi_\alpha$ is an ideal of \mathcal{X} for all $\alpha \in [-1, 0]$. For any $x \in \mathcal{X}$, let $\varphi(x) = \alpha$. Then, $x \in \varphi_\alpha$, and so φ_α is nonempty. Since φ_α is an ideal of \mathcal{X} , so $0 \in \varphi_\alpha$. Hence, $\varphi(0) \geq \alpha = \varphi(x)$ for all $x \in \mathcal{X}$. If there exists $a', b' \in \mathcal{X}$ such that

$$\varphi(a') < \min\{\varphi(a' * b'), \varphi(b')\}.$$

Then, by taking

$$\alpha_1 = \frac{1}{2}[\varphi(a') + \min\{\varphi(a' * b'), \varphi(b')\}],$$

we have

$$\varphi(a') < \alpha_1 < \min\{\varphi(a' * b'), \varphi(b')\}.$$

Hence, $a' \notin \varphi_{\alpha_1}$, $a' * b' \in \varphi_{\alpha_1}$ and $b' \in \varphi_{\alpha_1}$. This is a contradiction, and so $\varphi(x) \geq \min\{\varphi(x * y), \varphi(y)\}$ for all $x, y \in \mathcal{X}$. Therefore, (\mathcal{X}, φ) is a doubt \mathcal{N} -ideal of \mathcal{X} . \square

Theorem 3.11. *Let (\mathcal{X}, φ) be an \mathcal{N} -structure over \mathcal{X} . If the inequality $x * y \leq z$ holds in \mathcal{X} , then $\varphi(x) \geq \min\{\varphi(y), \varphi(z)\}$ for all $x, y, z \in \mathcal{X}$.*

Proof. (\mathcal{X}, φ) be an \mathcal{N} -structure over \mathcal{X} and $x, y, z \in \mathcal{X}$ be such that $x * y \leq z$. Then, $(x * y) * z = 0$, and so

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi(x) &\geq \min\{\varphi(x * y), \varphi(y)\} \\ &\geq \min\{\min\{\varphi((x * y) * z), \varphi(z)\}, \varphi(y)\} \\ &= \min\{\min\{\varphi(0), \varphi(z)\}, \varphi(y)\} \\ &= \min\{\varphi(y), \varphi(z)\}. \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. \square

Theorem 3.12. *Every doubt \mathcal{N} -ideal of \mathcal{X} is a doubt \mathcal{N} -subalgebra of \mathcal{X} .*

Proof. Let (\mathcal{X}, φ) be a doubt \mathcal{N} -ideal of \mathcal{X} . For any $x, y \in \mathcal{X}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi(x * y) &\geq \min\{\varphi((x * y) * x), \varphi(x)\} \\ &= \min\{\varphi((x * x) * y), \varphi(x)\} \\ &= \min\{\varphi(0 * y), \varphi(x)\} \\ &= \min\{\varphi(0), \varphi(x)\} \\ &\geq \min\{\varphi(x), \varphi(y)\} \end{aligned}$$

Hence, (\mathcal{X}, φ) is a doubt \mathcal{N} -subalgebra of \mathcal{X} . \square

Example 3.5. In Example 3.4, (\mathcal{X}, φ) is a doubt \mathcal{N} -ideal of \mathcal{X} , so that (\mathcal{X}, φ) is a doubt \mathcal{N} -subalgebra of \mathcal{X} .

The converse of Theorem 3.12 is not true in general.

Example 3.6. Consider a BCK -algebra $X = \{0, a, b, c, d\}$ with the following Cayley table:

*	0	a	b	c	d
0	0	0	0	0	0
a	a	0	0	0	0
b	b	a	0	a	0
c	c	c	c	0	0
d	d	d	d	c	0

Let (\mathcal{X}, φ) be an \mathcal{N} -structure in which φ is given by

$$\varphi(x) = \begin{cases} 0.0, & \text{if } x=0 \\ -0.2, & \text{if } x=a \\ -0.6, & \text{if } x=b \\ -0.4, & \text{if } x=c \\ -0.8, & \text{if } x=d. \end{cases}$$

Then, (\mathcal{X}, φ) is a doubt \mathcal{N} -subalgebra of \mathcal{X} , but it is not a doubt \mathcal{N} -ideal of \mathcal{X} since $\varphi(d) = -0.8 < -0.4 = \min\{\varphi(d * c), \varphi(c)\}$.

We give a condition for a doubt \mathcal{N} -subalgebra to be a doubt \mathcal{N} -ideal in a BCK -algebra.

Theorem 3.13. *Let (\mathcal{X}, φ) be a doubt \mathcal{N} -subalgebra of \mathcal{X} . If the inequality $x * y \leq z$ holds in \mathcal{X} , then (\mathcal{X}, φ) is a doubt \mathcal{N} -ideal of \mathcal{X} .*

Proof. Let (\mathcal{X}, φ) be a doubt \mathcal{N} -subalgebra of \mathcal{X} . Then, from Theorem 3.3, $\varphi(0) \geq \varphi(x)$, for all $x \in \mathcal{X}$. As $x * y \leq z$ holds in \mathcal{X} , then from Theorem 3.11, we get $\varphi(x) \geq \min\{\varphi(y), \varphi(z)\}$ for all $x, y, z \in \mathcal{X}$.

Since $x * (x * y) \leq y$ for all $x, y \in \mathcal{X}$, then $\varphi(x) \geq \min\{\varphi(x * y), \varphi(y)\}$. Hence, (\mathcal{X}, φ) is a doubt \mathcal{N} -ideal of \mathcal{X} . \square

Theorem 3.14. *Let (\mathcal{X}, φ) be a doubt \mathcal{N} -ideal of \mathcal{X} . Then, the set*

$$\mathcal{H} = \{x \in \mathcal{X} : \varphi(x) = \varphi(0)\}$$

is an ideal of \mathcal{X} .

Proof. Obviously, $0 \in \mathcal{H}$. Hence, $\mathcal{H} \neq \emptyset$. Now, let $x, y \in \mathcal{H}$ such that $x * y, y \in \mathcal{H}$. Then, $\varphi(x * y) = \varphi(0) = \varphi(y)$. Now, $\varphi(x) \geq \min\{\varphi(x * y), \varphi(y)\} = \varphi(0)$. Since (\mathcal{X}, φ) is a doubt \mathcal{N} -ideal of \mathcal{X} , $\varphi(0) \geq \varphi(x)$. Therefore, $\varphi(0) = \varphi(x)$. It follows that $x \in \mathcal{H}$, for all $x, y \in \mathcal{X}$. Therefore, \mathcal{H} is an ideal of \mathcal{X} . \square

For any element $\omega_\alpha \in X$, we consider the set:

$$\varphi_{\omega_\alpha} = \{x \in \mathcal{X} \mid \varphi(x) \geq \varphi(\omega_\alpha)\}.$$

Clearly, $\omega_\alpha \in \varphi_{\omega_\alpha}$. So that $\omega_\alpha \in \varphi_{\omega_\alpha}$ is a nonempty set of \mathcal{X} .

Theorem 3.15. *Let ω_α be any element of \mathcal{X} . If (\mathcal{X}, φ) is a doubt \mathcal{N} -ideal of X , then φ_{ω_α} is an ideal of \mathcal{X} .*

Proof. Clearly, $0 \in \varphi_{\omega_\alpha}$. Let $x, y \in \mathcal{X}$ be such that $x * y \in \varphi_{\omega_\alpha}$ and $y \in \varphi_{\omega_\alpha}$. Then, $\varphi(x * y) \geq \varphi(\omega_\alpha)$ and $\varphi(y) \geq \varphi(\omega_\alpha)$. It follows that from Definition 3.3, that

$$\varphi(x) \geq \min\{\varphi(x * y), \varphi(y)\} \geq \varphi(\omega_\alpha).$$

Hence, $x \in \varphi_{\omega_\alpha}$, and therefore φ_{ω_α} is an ideal of \mathcal{X} . \square

Theorem 3.16. *Let $\omega_\alpha \in \mathcal{X}$ and let (\mathcal{X}, φ) be an \mathcal{N} -structure over \mathcal{X} . Then,*

- (1) *If φ_{ω_α} is an ideal of \mathcal{X} , then the following assertion is valid for all $x, y, z \in X$:*
 - (A1) $\varphi(x) \leq \min\{\varphi(y * z), \varphi(z)\} \Rightarrow \varphi(x) \leq \varphi(y)$.
- (2) *If (\mathcal{X}, φ) satisfies (A1) and*
 - (A2) $\varphi(0) \geq \varphi(x)$

for all $x \in \mathcal{X}$. Then, φ_{ω_α} is an ideal for all $\omega_\alpha \in Im(\varphi)$.

Proof. (1) Assume that φ_{ω_α} is an ideal of \mathcal{X} for $\omega_\alpha \in \mathcal{X}$. Let $x, y, z \in \mathcal{X}$ be such that $\varphi(x) \leq \min\{\varphi(y * z), \varphi(z)\}$. Then, $y * z \in \varphi_{\omega_\alpha}$ and $z \in \varphi_{\omega_\alpha}$, where $\omega_\alpha = x$. Since φ_{ω_α} is an ideal of \mathcal{X} , it follows that $y \in \varphi_{\omega_\alpha}$ for $\omega_\alpha = x$. Hence, $\varphi(y) \geq \varphi(\omega_\alpha) = \varphi(x)$.

(2) Let $\omega_\alpha \in Im(\varphi)$ and suppose that (\mathcal{X}, φ) satisfies (A1) and (A2). Clearly, $0 \in \varphi_{\omega_\alpha}$ by (A2). Let $x, y \in \mathcal{X}$ be such that $x * y \in \varphi_{\omega_\alpha}$ and $y \in \varphi_{\omega_\alpha}$. Then, $\varphi(x * y) \geq \varphi(\omega_\alpha)$ and $\varphi(y) \geq \varphi(\omega_\alpha)$, so

$$\min\{\varphi(x * y), \varphi(y)\} \geq \varphi(\omega_\alpha).$$

It follows from (A1) that $\varphi(\omega_\alpha) \leq \varphi(x)$. Thus, $x \in \varphi_{\omega_\alpha}$, and therefore φ_{ω_α} is an ideal of \mathcal{X} . \square

4. CONCLUSIONS

Doubt \mathcal{N} -subalgebras and doubt \mathcal{N} -ideals with special properties play an important role in investigating the structure of an algebraic system. In this work, we discussed an \mathcal{N} -structure with an application to BCK -algebras. We introduced the notions of doubt \mathcal{N} -subalgebras and doubt \mathcal{N} -ideals in BCK -algebras, and investigated related properties. We considered some characterizations of a doubt \mathcal{N} -subalgebra and a doubt \mathcal{N} -ideal in BCK -algebras by means of doubt level subset. Relations between a doubt \mathcal{N} -subalgebra and a doubt \mathcal{N} -ideal were provided. We believe that our results presented in this paper will give a foundation for further study the algebraic structure of BCK -algebras.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are thankful to the editors and the anonymous reviewers for their valuable suggestions and comments on the manuscript.

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ANAS AL-MASARWAH

SCHOOL OF MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES, FACULTY OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, UNIVERSITI KEBANGSAAN MALAYSIA, 43600 UKM BANGI, SELANGOR DE, MALAYSIA

Email address: almasarwah85@gmail.com

ABD GHAFUR AHMAD

SCHOOL OF MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES, FACULTY OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, UNIVERSITI KEBANGSAAN
MALAYSIA, 43600 UKM BANGI, SELANGOR DE, MALAYSIA

Email address: ghafur@ukm.edu.my

G. MUHIUDDIN

DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICS, UNIVERSITY OF TABUK, TABUK 71491, SAUDI ARABIA

Email address: chishtygm@gmail.com